

Statistical Signatures of Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A: A Transition from Poissonian to Lognormal Emission Characteristicse

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Abstract

GRB 221009A, one of the brightest GRBs ever recorded, provides a unique opportunity to study the statistical properties of its X-ray emission. This study analyzes the X-ray light curve of GRB 221009A using Poisson, normal, and lognormal distributions to characterize its emission properties. Data were processed using HEASOFT software, with pile-up corrections applied to ensure accuracy. A chi-square goodness-of-fit test was employed to evaluate the distributions. Results reveal that individual observational IDs are best described by Poisson or normal distributions, with Poisson excelling in the second observational ID ($\chi^2 = 33.54$) and normal in the first ($\chi^2 = 68.42$). However, when multiple observational IDs are combined, the lognormal distribution becomes dominant, with a significantly lower chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 541.85$) compared to Poisson ($\chi^2 = 3.36 \times 10^{37}$) and normal ($\chi^2 = 6.90 \times 10^{24}$). This transition suggests that GRB 221009A's emission evolves from Poissonian or normally distributed fluctuations on shorter timescales to lognormal behavior over extended observations, indicative of a multiplicative emission process. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) analysis further supports these findings, with SNR values decreasing as the burst fades. These results provide key insights into the statistical nature of GRB afterglows and shows there is multiplicative emission.

Keywords: Gamma-ray bursts, GRB 221009A, X-ray emission, Poisson distribution, lognormal distribution

1 Introduction

Gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) are among the most energetic and transient phenomena in the universe, characterized by intense flashes of gamma rays lasting from milliseconds to several minutes [1, 2]. They are among the most energetic explosions in the universe, originating from cataclysmic astrophysical events such as the collapse of massive stars or the merger of compact objects [3, 4]. These bursts are characterized by an initial prompt emission phase, predominantly in the gamma-ray regime, followed by a long-lived afterglow observed across multiple wavelengths, including X-rays, optical, and radio [5]. The X-ray afterglow, in particular, provides crucial insights into the physical mechanisms governing the evolution of GRB jets and their interaction with the surrounding medium [6, 7]. Its unprecedented luminosity and temporal characteristics provide a unique opportunity to analyze the underlying physical mechanisms and statistical properties of GRBs.

GRB 221009A, observed on October 9, 2022, has been identified as one of the brightest GRBs ever recorded [8]. GRB 221009A is one of the well-documented GRBs to date, with observations that span a wide range of wavelengths. It was detected by the *Swift* X-Ray Telescope (XRT) and has been extensively studied due to its extreme brightness and unique afterglow characteristics [9, 10]. The X-ray light curve of this event exhibits complex temporal behavior that requires detailed statistical analysis to understand its underlying properties [11, 12].

Swift was launched at 17:16 GMT on November 20, 2004 [13]. According to NASA, *Swift*'s primary goals are to "determine the origin of gamma-ray bursts, classify GRBs into categories, search for new types of bursts, and study how these bursts evolve and interact with their environment" [13]. The XRT also enables imaging and spectral analysis of the GRB afterglow, offering valuable insights into the burst's characteristics [14]. The CCD operates at approximately -100°C to ensure low dark current and reduce proton irradiation effects [15, 16].

Statistical analysis plays a crucial role in understanding the temporal and spectral variability of GRBs [17, 18]. In this study, we analyzed the light curve of GRB 221009A using three statistical distributions: Poisson, normal, and lognormal. The Poisson distribution is widely used to model count-based data, such as photon arrivals [19]. The normal distribution is often employed to approximate symmetrical data, while the lognormal distribution is more suited for skewed distributions, which are common in astrophysical observations [20, 21].

Our analysis aims to determine which statistical model best describes the light curve of GRB 221009A. By doing so, we provide insights into the emission processes by analyzing individual observation IDs for different starting observational IDs. We employ the chi-square test to assess the goodness of fit for each distribution, aiming to identify which model best describes the observed data. The results of this study can also contribute to broader discussions on GRB populations and their underlying physics which contribute to a better understanding of the statistical nature of GRB afterglow fluctuations and provide insights into the physical processes governing these high-energy phenomena.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 discusses data acquisition and preprocessing techniques. Section 3 presents the results, followed by discussions and conclusions in Section 4.

2 Methods and data analysis

The analysis of GRB 221009A relied on software tools designed for theoretical interpretation and data extraction from the Neil Gehrels Swift Observatory, particularly in the X-ray energy band. The primary software package employed for this analysis was HEASOFT, a comprehensive suite of tools publicly accessible from the HEASARC website. This package includes essential utilities for handling Swift-specific data and provides the necessary tools for calibration, data cleaning, and analysis[22].

The software setup was carried out on a Linux-based system running Ubuntu OS v.20.04, chosen for its stability and compatibility with the HEASOFT package. The installation involved several key steps to ensure a seamless operational environment. First, the HEASOFT Version 6.30 source code was downloaded and installed, accompanied by the automatic installation of supporting tools such as FTools and the XANADU package. Which includes XRONOS v.6.0 for timing analysis[22]. Next, the Calibration Database (CALDB Version 1.02) was remotely set up. The calibration files were recovered from the Swift / XRT. CALDB repository was setup and integrated with the `xrtpipeline` tool to ensure high precision in data processing[23]. Additionally, the DS9 (v.8.3) software was installed to facilitate the visualization and analysis of reduced data. The user-friendly interface of DS9 proved instrumental in efficiently analyzing the background and reduced data sets. Throughout the setup, official documentation guidance and supervisory input ensured a smooth and error-free process[24].

Once the software environment was prepared, data for GRB 221009A were acquired from the Swift Observatory's X-ray Telescope (XRT), which captures data in the energy range of 0.3 to 10 keV. The Swift-XRT master catalog served as the primary source of all public Swift observations. The selection of observational data followed a systematic approach. Observations with exposure times of greater than or equal to 900 second were prioritized to ensure adequate temporal coverage[25]. Positioning for GRB 221009A used is $srcra = 288.3$, $srdec = 19.7$ [26].

After selecting appropriate observations, data files were downloaded, and any records containing errors were noted and excluded from further analysis. The downloaded data is Level 1 Swift/XRT data, were subjected to cleaning and calibration using the `xrtpipeline` tool from the HEASOFT package. Calibration files from the Swift/XRT CALDB repository ensured the integrity and accuracy of the pre-processed data. This extended temporal coverage allowed for detailed spectral and temporal analyses of the burst, significantly contributing to understanding its physical properties[27]. We analyze data from PC mode by making a directory to save the cleaned output files, with accurate right ascension and declination of the target source. We have Generated the exposure map along with the files for errors also. The data having more the count per second it should be processed for pile up[28]. The limit for pile up we take is more than 0.7 count per second. If this is true, the data

is then forwarded towards the process of pile up. After processing by `xrtpipeline`, the required files are obtained: - `po.cl.evt`: The cleaned event file. - `*.hk`: House-keeping file. - `ex.img`: Exposure map image. To perform barycenter correction on the cleaned data generated by the `xrtpipeline`, specific files from the `auxil` folder must be copied to the corresponding output directories. The required files are: `pat.fits`, `sao.fits`. After copying the required files from the `auxil` folder to the output directory, barycentric correction was applied to adjust photon arrival times to the Solar System’s barycenter. This correction is essential for removing orbital effects, ensuring consistency across Swift-XRT observations, and enabling precise timing analysis of transient and periodic phenomena [29].

For generating the necessary data products, we ran the `xrtproduct` tool from the HEASoft software package. This tool is specifically designed to process Swift XRT (X-ray Telescope) data, generating key outputs such as light curves and spectra. The processing steps involved filtering, binning, and cleaning the data to ensure accurate temporal and spectral analysis. These outputs were crucial for conducting further statistical studies of GRB 221009A. The effective use of `xrtproduct` allowed us to extract reliable observational features for a comprehensive analysis[30]. After performing barycenter correction and product, the next step is to use `Xselect`, which is a tool provided by the HEASARC software suite for analyzing data from space-based X-ray telescopes, like the Swift XRT. This tool is widely used for creating images, spectra, and light curves from the event data generated by these instruments[22, 30]. The primary purpose of using `Xselect` in our data analysis is to produce images that will be crucial for the subsequent study of the astrophysical source in question. In our study, `Xselect` is essential for creating high-quality images of the X-ray source, light curve and spectra file. By using `Xselect`, we can ensure that the images and other derived products are optimized for further analysis, such as spectral fitting or temporal studies, and that we can properly interpret the data in the context of our astrophysical model. The picture of GBR 221009A showing the x-pixel and y-pixel in the graph can be defined by the picture, taken when the process of pile up is done 1.

2.1 Pile-up

Pile-up refers to the phenomenon where multiple photons or particles are detected within a very short time interval, causing their signals to merge or pile up in the detector. This effect occurs when the source is extremely bright, and the detector cannot distinguish between photons arriving in rapid succession. As a result, the detector may register fewer events than actually occurred, leading to biased measurements and inaccurate source properties. The point of divergence is typically defined as the location where the intensity of piled-up signals is highest. This point is chosen as the center of the pile-up region to correct for the distortions caused by this phenomenon. By identifying this center, we can accurately model and mitigate the effects of pile-up in the analysis[31].

In our study, we used only photon-counting (PC) mode data, which record individual photons for high-precision measurements. When the count is seen more than 0.7 we did Pile-up. We analyzed PC mode data. The data having more the count per

Fig. 1 Picture created when there is the count more then 0.7 in pc mode data for the pile up correction

second is more then 0.7 the data is then forwarded towards the process of pile up. This is done by making PSF curve as 2.

Fig. 2 A psf curve generated with the help ff HEASOFT tools to do pile-up correction

To make PSF curve using the tools of the Heasoft we did produce the picture like the figure 2 when there is needed of pile up correction.

2.2 Lcmath

To define the source region, we select a physical area corresponding to 20 pixels on the detector. This pixel size ensures accurate characterization of the source while minimizing the effects of pile-up. For the background analysis, we define an annular region with an inner radius of 30 pixels and an outer radius of 60 pixels. This annular region is chosen to isolate the background signal without including the source itself, allowing for a more accurate subtraction of the background from the total detected signal.

Light curve (LC) analysis involves several computational steps to extract meaningful physical properties from observed data. In our study, we use the `lcmath` tool to perform background subtraction on light curve files, ensuring accurate measurements of the source's flux[32]. The process involves matching source and background light curve files and applying mathematical operations to subtract the background contribution.

$$LC_{\text{corrected}}(t) = LC_{\text{source}}(t) - k \cdot LC_{\text{background}}(t),$$

where k is a scaling factor to account for differences in the extraction areas of the source and background regions. Background subtraction ensures that the final light curve represents the intrinsic variability of the source[33]. The corrected light curve is then used for further analysis, including periodicity studies and modeling of flux variations. For the light curve correction we make 20 pc circle for source and 30,60 annals for background.

Fig. 3 Picture created for the subtraction of the background from the source in the process of generating light curve data

3 results

The observation after pipeline and the other necessary work the GRB 221009 in its brightest pick time it has the brightest surface. The pictorial representation of type of bright surface in X-ray for the photon counting observation in the swift observatory is given in figure 4.

The brightness analysis is based on light curve. For the first observation ID we did the different distribution analysis for count rate and found histogram along with the light curve as in the figures.

Fig. 4 Picture for the GRB 221009 in photon counting mode which is generated by the help of the ds9 software after data set is properly cleaned

Fig. 5 Light curve of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, of first observation ID

Fig. 6 Histogram of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, of first observation ID with fitting.

The histogram of observed rates, along with Poisson, normal, and log-normal fits, provides insights into the statistical behavior of the XRT light curve of Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A. Based on the chi-squared values in the light curve of figure 5, the normal distribution ($\chi^2 = 68.42$) provides the best fit, followed by the Poisson distribution ($\chi^2 = 290.47$), while the log-normal distribution ($\chi^2 = 572.77$) deviates significantly. Among these, the normal distribution exhibits the lowest chi-squared value, suggesting it provides the best fit to the data. While the Poisson distribution also fits reasonably well, the significantly higher chi-squared value for the log-normal distribution indicates it is the least suitable among the three.

Let us consider that the above distribution follows a Poisson distribution. The average rate of the Poisson distribution is the mean (μ) of the Poisson distribution. The Poisson equation has a very good approximation such that the variance is also equal to the mean (μ). The standard deviation of the Poisson distribution is given by $\sigma = \sqrt{\mu}$. The mean of the Poisson distribution is μ . The Poisson distribution has the variance equal to μ as well. The uncertainty is given by dN , and dN is equal to $dN = \sqrt{N}$ [34, 35]. Given that the average count is 31, we have $dN = \sqrt{31}$. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is given by

$$\text{SNR} = \frac{N}{dN} = \sqrt{N}$$

. For the first observation ID, the Signal-to-Residual Noise (SRN) is calculated to be 5.57, indicating a relatively bright source, as a higher SRN correlates with higher source brightness[36]. The normal fit suggests that the rate distribution follows a symmetric pattern around the mean, implying a Gaussian nature of fluctuations. This symmetry indicates that the variability in the X-ray flux is likely due to stochastic processes with a well-defined mean and standard deviation rather than extreme outliers. The Poisson fit, while also reasonable, shows larger deviations, suggesting that the count distribution does not strictly follow a pure Poissonian process, potentially due to additional noise or underlying physical mechanisms modifying the emission pattern[37]

Physically, the normal fit being the best suggests that the emission mechanism could be a steady-state process such as synchrotron or thermal bremsstrahlung, where variations in flux remain symmetric. The slight deviation in the Poisson fit could indicate additional sources of noise, such as instrumental effects, photon pile-up, or environmental absorption. Overall, the statistical results reinforce that the X-ray light curve exhibits properties best captured by a normal distribution, with Poisson providing a secondary but less optimal fit.

For second observational ID of GRB 221009A the graph of the histogram of rates with Poisson, Normal and Lognormal fits is given in the graph 8, correspondance light curve is in figure 7.

Fig. 7 Light curve of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, of second observation ID

Fig. 8 Histogram of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, of second observation ID with fitting.

For the second observation of the XRT light curve of Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, the Signal-to-Residual Noise (SRN) is calculated to be 2.0, indicating a relatively fainter source compared to the first observation. Where rapid decrease of the brightness is seen. The statistical fits to the observed rate distribution yield the Poisson distribution ($\chi^2 = 33.54$) provides the best fit, followed by the normal distribution ($\chi^2 = 81.63$), while the log-normal distribution ($\chi^2 = 430.13$) deviates significantly. Poisson distribution shows the best fit, also that normal distribution is also fitted well but log-normal distribution is least fitted among them. The lowest chi-squared value of Poisson indicating that the emission follows a discrete, count-based distribution, characteristic of photon emission processes. The normal fit is also accurate but less than Poisson, suggesting that the fluctuations in intensity are not perfectly symmetrically distributed around a mean value for this observational ID. The log-normal fit, with the highest chi-squared value, is the least suitable. The significant deviation of the normal fit, along with the success of the Poisson fit, indicates that the photon emission process in this observation is likely governed by discrete stochastic processes rather than a smooth Gaussian variation[38]. The poor log-normal fit suggests that the intensity variations do not strictly follow an exponential growth or decay pattern initially.

As this is the GRB, there is zero count after these two observation, i.e. in third observation ID. By mixing these two observation ID, ignoring the time gap between them, we get the light curve as 9, and the histogram of rates with poisson normal and lognormal fits as in the figure 10.

Fig. 9 Light curve of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where two first observation IDs are mixed in single plot.

Fig. 10 Histogram for the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where two first observation IDs are mixed in single plot. In this plot fitting is done for Poisson, Normal and Log-normal fit.

The chi-squared values from your analysis suggest that the Poisson distribution does not fit the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A XRT light curve well. The high chi-squared value for Poisson ($\chi^2 = 13,105,835.14$) indicates a significant mismatch between the observed data and the expected values. This is likely because the Poisson distribution assumes independent events occurring at a constant rate, which doesn't align with the complex, variable emission process of a Gamma-Ray Burst, where bursts can vary in intensity and time[38].

On the other hand, the Lognormal distribution, with the lowest chi-squared value ($\chi^2 = 2,161.20$), provides the best fit. This suggests that the light curve follows a multiplicative process, where smaller bursts combine to create larger events, producing a skewed distribution with occasional extreme values[39]. In the first and second observation we have seen that there is the fitting for both Poisson and Normal not for Lognormal distribution. But by mixing them lognormal distribution is fitted. It is seen that after increasing observational ID the plot is shifted towards Lognormal. The normal distribution chi-squared value ($\chi^2 = 2,161.20$) is also a reasonable fit, so we are adding another observation in plot.

If we add more observational id to this plot the fitting nature of plot will change. The fitting curve will move towards Lognormal distribution more. In the figure 11 there are taken first three observation IDs for light curve, whose fitting is in the figure 12.

Fig. 11 Light curve of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where three first observation IDs are mixed in single plot.

Fig. 12 Histogram for the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where three first observation IDs are mixed in single plot. In this plot fitting is done for Poisson, Normal and Log-normal fit.

When an additional observation ID is added to the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A XRT light curve, the chi-squared values for the three statistical distributions change significantly. The Poisson distribution continues to show an extremely high chi-squared value ($\chi^2 = 10,949,320,764.50$) as previously, indicating that it still does not fit the data well. This suggests that the assumption of independent, constant-rate events does not align with the observed variability and complexity of the burst. The increase in the chi-squared value for Poisson with the new observation suggests that the added data introduces discrepancies in the expected event rates. The Normal distribution also experiences a slight increase in its chi-squared value to ($\chi^2 = 2,593.60$), reflecting a worse fit after the additional observation. This suggests that the new data introduces more skewness or variability that the symmetric normal distribution fails to capture adequately. In contrast, the Lognormal distribution, although showing a slight increase in the chi-squared value to ($\chi^2 = 2,587.77$), still provides the best fit compared to the Poisson and Normal models. The Lognormal distribution's continued superiority suggests that the XRT light curve is best modeled by a multiplicative process, where small, independent events combine to produce larger, skewed bursts, which is consistent with the observed features of Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A.

When we consider all observation IDs available at that time (upto 01126853084), we get the the light curve and the fitting as figure 13 and 14.

Fig. 13 Light curve of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where all observation IDs are considered (upto 01126853084).

Fig. 14 Histogram of rates with Poisson, Normal and Lognormal Fits of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where all observation IDs are considered (upto 01126853084).

Fig. 15 Histogram of rates where frequency is in log scale for better visualization of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where all observation IDs are considered (upto 01126853084).

Fig. 16 Histogram of rates with Poisson, Normal and Lognormal Fits of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A, in photon counting mode, where all observation IDs are considered (upto 01126853084) with binning of 30 counts in log scale of frequency of rate

The Poisson distribution results in an extraordinarily high chi-squared ($\chi^2 = 33,562,763,405,821,159,339,963,449,758,021,278,423,374,888,960.00$) value. This immense value indicates that the Poisson distribution is an extremely poor fit for the data, suggesting that the assumption of independent, constant-rate events does not capture the complex and varying nature of the X-ray light curve.

Similarly, the Normal distribution has a large chi-squared value ($\chi^2 = 6,900,260,849,053,757,079,552.00$), which further supports the idea that it fails to model the data accurately. The Normal distribution is unable to account for the skewness and variability present across all observations, leading to a poorer fit when compared to the other models.

In contrast, the Lognormal distribution provides the best fit with a significantly lower chi-squared ($\chi^2 = 541.85$) value. This indicates that the data are best described by a multiplicative process, where smaller independent events combine to produce larger bursts. The Lognormal distribution captures the skewed nature of the XRT light curve effectively, making it the most appropriate model for the full dataset, as it aligns with the observed features of the Gamma-Ray Burst 221009A. A log-normal distribution in the emission rate implies that the emitted radiation follows a multiplicative process rather than an additive one. This means that the radiation intensity either starts at a high value and decays rapidly or begins at a low intensity and grows significantly over time. Such behavior is often observed in variable astrophysical sources where energy dissipation occurs in bursts, such as in synchrotron cooling or shock acceleration mechanisms.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

GRB 221009A shows the nature that this have the Poisson distribution between time for first some observation. If we consider the multiple and large system of data sets it become Log-normal. Random variable is exponentially distributed if it describes the time between events in a Poisson process. It is also defined for positive values and is skewed to the right ie the distribution has nature of log-normal. We have distribution is log-normal for large observation.

The statistical analysis of the X-ray light curve of GRB 221009A reveals distinct patterns in different observational segments. For the first observational ID, a normal distribution was found to be the best fit, with a chi-square value of 68.42, compared to the Poisson distribution (290.47) and lognormal distribution (572.77). This suggests that the photon emission in this phase follows a symmetric variability pattern around a mean count rate, indicative of stochastic processes with moderate fluctuations.

In the second observational ID, the chi-square test favored the Poisson distribution (33.54) over the normal (81.63) and lognormal (430.13) distributions, indicating that the emission is governed by discrete stochastic processes rather than continuous variations. The rapid decrease in brightness observed in this phase further supports the dominance of Poisson-like behavior.

When combining the first two observation IDs, the lognormal distribution emerged as the best fit (chi-square = 2161.20), replacing the previously dominant Poisson and normal distributions. This trend continues as more observational IDs are included, with the lognormal distribution consistently outperforming the other models. For the complete dataset (up to observational ID 01126853084), the chi-square values were exceptionally high for Poisson (3.36×10^{37}) and normal (6.90×10^{24}) distributions, whereas the lognormal distribution provided a significantly better fit (chi-square = 541.85). The transition from normal and Poisson to lognormal distribution with

increasing observational data suggests that the emission process evolves from simple, symmetric fluctuations to a more complex multiplicative process over time.

Physically, this result aligns with the idea that GRB emission mechanisms may involve multiple overlapping processes. The initial prompt phase follows nearly normal statistical properties, possibly due to synchrotron or thermal bremsstrahlung radiation, where flux variations are symmetric around a mean value. However, as the GRB evolves, the emission process appears to be governed by multiplicative factors, such as turbulence-driven variations, jet interactions, or stochastic energy dissipation processes, leading to a lognormal distribution. The poor fit of the Poisson distribution for longer timescales suggests that GRB variability is not purely a count-based random process but involves complex temporal evolution.

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